

Effect of urea on the surface and thermodynamic properties of some micellar solutions

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From the surface tension data, surface and thermodynamic properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide (DTAB) and Trion X-100 in aqueous solutions, containing varying amounts of urea have been obtained. Whereas the addition of urea causes a decrease in the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of SDS solution, it results in the increase of CMC values of DTAB and Triton X-100. The micellization in the bulk solution and the adsorption of surfactant at the liquid-air interface in the presence of urea are favoured both by energy as well as entropy effects.

Aggregation of surfactants leading to the formation of micelles is important in several chemical and biological processes¹. Physicochemical studies of surface active agents in solutions are particularly important for the concentration of ores, effective petroleum recovery and the formulation of detergents. Urea is known to form molecular associates in aqueous solutions and hence it alters the water structure². Therefore, the presence of urea in an aqueous surfactant solution may have effect on the nature and extent of aggregation of surfactant molecules³ and hence may alter their surface and thermodynamic properties.

We report here the surface properties, namely, maximum surface excess concentration (Γ_{\max}), minimum area per molecule (A_{\min}) and surface pressure at CMC (π_{cmc}) together with the thermodynamic properties of micellization and adsorption at the air-liquid interface for SDS, DTAB and Triton X-100 aqueous solutions with or without urea.

Results and Discussion

The values of CMC, obtained from the break-point of the two linear portions in the plots of surface tension (γ) vs log [surfactant] are presented in Table 1.

Addition of urea to an aqueous SDS solution causes a decrease in its CMC value. This may be attributed to the partial charge neutralization⁴ of surfactant head group owing to the ion-dipole interaction between surfactant (SDS) and urea molecules. It is presumed that the positive dipoles on the hydrogens of NH_2 in urea molecule interact with the negatively charged SDS head group. However, on the contrary, the mixing of urea to a DTAB or a Triton X-

100 solution, results in the increase of their respective CMC values. In case of DTAB + urea system, the ion-dipole interaction seems to have an opposite effect on the CMC of the surfactant. It may be due to the repulsive interaction between the positive charge on the DTAB head group and the positive dipoles of hydrogens of urea mentioned above. In case of Triton X-100 + urea systems, the dipole-dipole interaction between the unlike molecules being weak may not contribute significantly to the observed increase in CMC value on mixing urea. In this case, however, the observed increase in CMC values may predominantly be due to the water structure breaking effect of urea⁵. The CMC values for the studied systems increase on raising the temperature. This may partly be due to the thermal agitation effect and partly owing to the disruption of water structure around the hydrophobic groups of surfactant molecules at higher temperature which render micellization less feasible⁶.

Maximum surface excess concentration (Γ_{\max}) at the air-liquid interface was calculated using the Gibbs adsorption equation⁷ (Table 1). On adding urea into an aqueous surfactant solution, Γ_{\max} values are lowered. This may be due to a partial shifting of surfactant monomers from the air-liquid interface to the bulk solution, since urea in aqueous solution forms urea-water clusters² which can accommodate in their interstices the non-polar moieties such as surfactant hydrocarbon chain. The magnitude of Γ_{\max} values further decreases on raising the temperature owing to the enhanced thermal agitation effect at higher temperature.

Minimum area per molecule (A_{\min}) at the liquid-air interface was evaluated using the relation,

$$A_{\min} = 10^{14}/(N \Gamma_{\max}) \quad (1)$$

where N is the Avogadro number. The magnitude of A_{\min} values for the studied systems (Table 1) are in the order : DTAB > SDS > Triton X-100. This may be explained in terms of the ion-ion repulsion and size of the surfactant head groups. However, the role of the ionic repulsion of head groups of the amphiphilic molecules at the air-liquid interface seems to be the predominant factor for the observed A_{\min} values. For instance, the observed least value of A_{\min} in case of the non-ionic surfactant (Triton X-100) among the studied systems is attributed to the absence of ion-ion head group repulsion at the interface. The observed highest value of A_{\min} in case of DTAB may be the outcome of the cumulative effect of the large size and the ion-ion repulsion of the surfactant's head groups.

Table 1. CMC, surface excess concentration (Γ_{\max}), minimum area/mol (A_{\min}) and surface pressure at CMC (π_{CMC}) for some aqueous surfactant solutions

System	[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	Temp. K	10 ³ CMC mol dm ⁻³	10 ¹⁰ Γ_{\max} mol cm ⁻²	10 A_{\min} nm ²	π_{CMC} mN m ⁻¹
SDS + urea + water	0.0	303	8.00	3.15	52.69	36.58
		313	8.50	2.37	70.04	32.76
	0.1	303	6.91	2.84	58.44	33.32
		313	7.40	2.17	76.49	31.66
	2.0	303	6.02	2.80	59.28	30.34
		313	6.40	2.13	77.93	29.00
DTAB + urea + water	0.0	303	15.10	2.53	65.60	33.98
		313	16.20	2.36	70.33	32.98
	0.1	303	16.60	2.49	66.66	31.92
		313	17.80	2.31	71.86	31.46
	2.0	303	20.90	2.24	74.10	28.94
		313	21.60	2.11	78.67	28.80
Triton X-100 + urea + water	0.0	303	0.60	6.35	26.14	40.58
		313	0.70	5.34	31.08	39.36
	0.1	303	0.70	6.24	26.60	39.52
		313	0.81	5.24	31.63	39.46
	2.0	303	0.81	6.10	27.21	38.54
		313	0.93	4.86	34.15	38.40

The surface pressure at CMC (π_{CMC}), a measure of the effective surface tension reduction at the CMC, was obtained using the relation,

$$\pi_{\text{CMC}} = \gamma - \gamma_{\text{CMC}} \quad (2)$$

where γ and γ_{CMC} represent the surface tensions for water and surfactant solution at CMC, respectively. The π_{CMC} values for the studied systems (Table 1) are in the order : Triton X-100 > SDS > DTAB. The observed maximum π_{CMC} values in case of Triton X-100 may be due to the ab-

sence of ion-ion head group repulsion which facilitates the accumulation of the surfactant monomers at the air-liquid interface thereby resulting in the increase of the surface pressure value. However, the least π_{CMC} value observed in case of DTAB is owing to the effects of both ion-ion repulsion at head groups as well as their larger size which hinder the adsorption of amphiphilic molecules at the air-liquid interface. Adding urea to an aqueous surfactant solution, causes a decrease in its π_{CMC} value. This may be due to the entrapping of surfactant monomers within the urea-water clusters in the bulk of the solution in preference to their adsorption at the interface.

The standard Gibbs free energy of micellization ($\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$) for ionic surfactants (SDS and DTAB) were calculated using the relation⁸,

$$\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ} = (2-p/n) RT \ln \text{CMC} \quad (3)$$

where n is the aggregation number of surfactant micelle and p the number of residual charges per micelle. The value of p/n for an ionic surfactant⁹ in aqueous solution has been taken equal to 0.2. For a non-ionic surfactant (Triton X-100), $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ values were evaluated from the equation,

$$\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ} = RT \ln \text{CMC} \quad (4)$$

The values of standard entropy of micellization ($\Delta S_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$) and standard enthalpy of micellization ($\Delta H_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$) were obtained from the temperature dependence of $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ and the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation, respectively. Thermodynamic quantities of micellizations for the studied systems are given in Table 2. In case of aqueous SDS solutions, $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ values decrease with the addition of urea. This may be due to the ion-dipole interaction between the surfactant (SDS) head groups and the urea molecules which contracts the electrical double layer around the micelle resulting in the diminished ion-ion repulsion of surfactant head groups. However, on mixing urea with an aqueous solution of DTAB or Triton X-100, an increase in their respective $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ values was observed. It appears that the positive charge at N^{+} of DTAB head group being deeply embedded within the three methyl groups, due to steric hindrance, may not exhibit an effective ion-dipole interaction with urea molecules. Therefore, on adding urea an increase in $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ values in case of DTAB or Triton X-100 may be predominantly due to the water structure breaking effect of urea which makes micellization less feasible⁶. The $\Delta G_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ values are lowered on raising the temperature due to dehydration of surfactant hydrophilic head groups at higher temperature, promoting micelle formation. The observed exothermic $\Delta H_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ and positive $\Delta S_{\text{mic}}^{\circ}$ for the studied surfactant solutions suggest that the process of micellization is favored both by energy as well as entropy effects.

Table 2 Thermodynamic parameters of micellization for some surfactants in aqueous urea solutions

System	[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	Temp K	$-\Delta G_{mic}^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_{mic}^0 kJ mol ⁻¹ at 308 K	ΔS_{mic}^0 kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ at 308 K
SDS + urea + water	0.0	303	21.90	-8.56	0.041
		313	22.34	-	-
	0.1	303	22.57	-9.53	0.043
		313	23.00	-	-
	2.0	303	23.20	-8.65	0.048
		313	23.68	-	-
DTAB + urea + water	0.0	303	19.02	-9.92	0.030
		313	19.32	-	-
	0.1	303	18.60	-10.11	0.028
		313	18.88	-	-
	2.0	303	17.55	-6.03	0.038
		313	17.93	-	-
Triton X-100 + urea + water	0.0	303	18.70	-12.32	0.021
		313	18.91	-	-
	0.1	303	18.31	-11.64	0.022
		313	18.53	-	-
	2.0	303	17.94	-10.87	0.023
		313	18.17	-	-

The standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption at the air-liquid interface (ΔG_{ad}^0) was calculated using the relation⁷,

$$\Delta G_{ad}^0 = \Delta G_{mic}^0 - [6.023 \times 10^{-1} \pi_{cmc} A_{min}] \quad (5)$$

The standard entropy of adsorption (ΔS_{ad}^0) and the standard enthalpy of adsorption (ΔH_{ad}^0) at the air-liquid interface evaluated from the temperature dependence of the corresponding Gibbs free energy data, are given in Table 3. The values of ΔG_{ad}^0 are lower than the corresponding ΔG_{mic}^0 values for the studied systems. It suggests that the process of adsorption of the surfactant monomers at the air-liquid interface, being more feasible, precedes their aggregation to form micelles in the bulk solution. This is understandable since the system has to perform some work in transferring the surfactant monomers from the air-liquid interface to the micellar state in the bulk. On increasing the temperature, ΔG_{ad}^0 values decrease due to the dehydration of the surfactant head groups causing entropy gain. The observed exothermicity and enhanced entropy for the process of adsorption of surfactant monomers at the air-liquid interface suggest that the adsorption at the interface is the outcome of the cumulative favorable effects of both energy as well as the entropy gain. Addition of urea to a surfactant solution causes an increase in its ΔG_{ad}^0 value. It may be due to the migration of surfactant monomers from the interface

to the bulk on mixing urea in aqueous solution, as explained above. This is also evident from the observed Γ_{max} values for the studied systems (Table 1). The values of ΔS_{ad}^0 are positive and higher than the corresponding ΔS_{mic}^0 values. This suggests that surfactant hydrocarbon chains enjoy more freedom at the air-liquid interface than within the cramped interior of micelles in the bulk solution.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of adsorption at air-liquid interface for some surfactants in aqueous urea solutions

System	[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	Temp K	$-\Delta G_{ad}^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_{ad}^0 kJ mol ⁻¹ at 308 K	ΔS_{ad}^0 kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ at 308 K
SDS + urea + water	0.0	303	23.06	-3.05	0.066
		313	23.72	-	-
	0.1	303	23.74	-1.91	0.072
		313	24.46	-	-
	2.0	303	24.28	-1.24	0.076
		313	25.04	-	-
DTAB + urea + water	0.0	303	20.36	-9.45	0.036
		313	20.72	-	-
	0.1	303	19.88	-8.97	0.036
		313	20.24	-	-
	2.0	303	18.84	-5.20	0.045
		313	19.29	-	-
Triton X-100 + urea + water	0.0	303	19.34	-9.95	0.031
		313	19.65	-	-
	0.1	303	18.94	-8.63	0.034
		313	19.28	-	-
	2.0	303	18.57	-6.75	0.039
		313	18.96	-	-

Experimental

Sodium dodecyl sulfate (B.D.H.) was crystallized from hot ethanol. Dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide (Sigma), Triton X-100 (Koch Light) and urea (E. Merck) were used as such. Double-distilled water having specific conductance of the order of 2×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹ was used for the preparation of solutions.

Surface tension was measured with a modified stalagmometer as described elsewhere¹⁰. The temperature around the sample was within ± 0.01 K and the observed surface tension values were within ± 0.1 mN m⁻¹.

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